

[#131, Prison director]

I was informed in the afternoon that a foreign prisoner was late from external work, in a bar near the Town. Even though the Department activated its security checks, it wasn't possible to track down the prisoner who, after 12 hours, was declared a fugitive. This resulted in further inspections and more intensive searches, but by then the escape had occurred. With regard to the dynamics, the prisoner also had plenty of time to organise things. The way we manage inmates external work didn't allow us to avoid what happened.

We felt fear, disappointment, helplessness. We felt regret anyway, although it was an escape happened outside the prison.

I believe that the constant dialogue with the educational area can allow the director to assess more clearly the situations, even predictable ones, according on to the tendency of the inmate. Both well-knowing the inmate and external control should always be a continuous process governed by multidisciplinary discussion. If different professional areas work in sealed compartments, it is impossible to identify those individual indicators that would give rise to a gauge other than the one actually gave. This requires a great commitment and effort to overcome established practices, the habit of working alone for certain areas. When the criticality occurs, the responsibility lies with everyone.

[#215, Police commander]

The prisoner, desperate because having been left by his wife after his arrest, decided to commit suicide and cut his throat with a razor blade. Being saved in extremis, he came back from hospital terribly distressed and showed strong signs of atrocious suffering, so that all of us kept a very high level of attention. We also alerted the two cellmates, who did nightshifts to monitor the inmate. The greatest problem was morning him during the walking in the yards.

The meetings followed one another, to develop the best strategies to avoid the worst. The prisoner was assigned to the teacher of the lecturing class, in order to keep him busy in the morning, to push away the idea of dying and to get him more involved in the visits.

At first, we felt very frustrated, but in the end, we were satisfied with the final result related to the proper involvement of the various operators, who felt a team; and also, for the positive response we received from his cellmates who, despite not having been trained for this, immediately understood the importance of their role in that situation.

At the end of this story, I've the growing awareness of the need for a high level of attention and for the necessary involvement of all the staff, who must feel part of the group, always and in every critical situation.
